

D4.6

DRAFT POLICY DOCUMENT FOR COMMON SERVICE CATALOGUE (ENVRI POLICY FRAMEWORK)

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Deliverable abstract

This document presents the move from a theoretical policy framework, derived from Workshop 1 and discussed at Workshop 2, towards a practical implementation of policy. It starts with the analysis of key policy drivers (EOSC Rules of participation, FAIR principles and ENVRI-Hub initial documents) in the respect of organisational decisions (“Policy drivers”) needed from an ENVRI RI. The document collects these main policy statements (i.e., the “core” of the policy documents) into a draft framework, including other implied policies derived from the core requirements. The document also includes considerations of differences between Policies, Practices (Guidelines) and Technologies (IT Implementation) in Research Infrastructure management and maintenance, as well as some common requirements for interoperable and documentable policy documents. To move from this position to a practical implementation, Workshop 3 demonstrated how we can create policies (and subsequently guidelines and IT implementation) starting from the policy statements but creating policy documents. The policy documents of various RIs were compared, and the policy document template of EPOS, together with other examples, informed the discussion. In parallel, a landscape analysis leading to D4.5 should provide a state-of-the-art view across the participating RIs, from which policies suitable for the ENVRI-Hub (to interoperate across ENVRI RIs and also with EOSC) and their congruency can be analysed. Due to the delays with D4.5, this deliverable documents the path to draft policies for the ENVRI-Hub. In Workshop 4 (which leads to D4.7) these results will be discussed and the move to the final ENVRI policies planned.

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DOCUMENT AMENDMENT PROCEDURE

Amendments, comments and suggestions should be sent to the Project Manager at manager@envri-fair.eu.

GLOSSARY

A relevant project glossary is included in Appendix A. The latest version of the master list of the glossary is available at <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4471374>.

PROJECT SUMMARY

ENVRI-FAIR is the connection of the ESFRI Cluster of Environmental Research Infrastructures (ENVRI) to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Participating research infrastructures (RI) of the environmental domain cover the subdomains Atmosphere, Marine, Solid Earth, and Biodiversity / Ecosystems and thus the Earth system in its full complexity.

The overarching goal is that at the end of the proposed project, all participating RIs have built a set of FAIR data services which enhances the efficiency and productivity of researchers, supports innovation, enables data- and knowledge-based decisions, and connects the ENVRI Cluster to the EOSC.

This goal is reached by: (1) well defined community policies and standards on all steps of the data life cycle, aligned with the wider European policies, as well as with international developments; (2) each participating RI will have sustainable, transparent, and auditable data services, for each step of data life cycle, compliant to the FAIR principles. (3) the focus of the proposed work is put on the implementation of prototypes for testing pre-production services at each RI; the catalogue of prepared services is defined for each RI independently, depending on the maturity of the involved RIs; (4) the complete set of thematic data services and tools provided by the ENVRI cluster is exposed under the EOSC catalogue of services.

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D4.6. Draft policy document for common service catalogue – A Policy framework for ENVRI service provision towards EOSC

1. Introduction

1.1 Rationale

European Open Science Cloud, FAIR principles, and operational project requirements of ENVRI FAIR all require several changes in the data systems of the ENVRI research infrastructures. These demands are not, however, only concentrated on the purely technical aspects, and can require significant changes in the operations and the policies of the participating RIs. Emerging and existing international and national laws also provide additional constraints. As one of the key aspects of these developments is the perceived need for further interoperability, building a common and interoperable platform for these policies would be beneficial. This document presents the first iteration of such policy framework in action.

Major international research infrastructures that are included in the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) Road Map are science-oriented organizations that aim to deliver data services for researchers. They are commonly built “bottom-up” from the requirements and needs of the research communities they serve, and thus a lot of domain-specific leadership of these organizations have their foundations in the relevant associated science areas. From the organizational point of view, such an approach has many advantages, as the staff are well accustomed to issues related to the infrastructure customers (researchers). However, there are additional challenges related to the administrative and leadership experience needed by the organizations (*management debt*), and many training activities have been initiated at the European and local level to address this issue.

One of the required competences is understanding the need for policy development within these organizations, and the target of this deliverable is to define a path to a draft policy for the common catalogue of digital assets (DA) of the ENVRI-Hub. Along the way it provides some general guidance on policies, and the creation of a common framework to distribute experiences and knowledge across the RI cluster. This is to ensure minimal discontinuity between the policies associated with ENVRI-Hub and those of the RIs and their asset suppliers. Such discontinuities cause friction in interoperability and may even preclude interoperation. As even the term “policy” is not well defined in this context, this document also includes the working definitions used within this context and specifies which level of communality can be expected in this kind of policy statement.

1.2 Target audiences

The main target audiences for this document are (in order):

1. Managers of the ENVRI-Hub who need to have responsibility for the policy framework within which the ENVRI-Hub operates;
2. Technical developers of the ENVRI-Hub who need to ensure the policies are supported/enforced by the software and processes of ENVRI-Hub;
3. Management staff of the ENVRI RIs (including nascent research infrastructures), particularly staff working between the high-level decision making and practical application level in the research infrastructures. They are approached in their role to develop these Policy decisions, and to create associated practices within their organizations.
4. Strategic leadership of ENVRI RIs, from Director Generals (or similar) to their high-level direction groups (General Assemblies and similar bodies, often representatives of Member States). They are included as they are often responsible for determining the strategic importance of policies and approving them for their organizations.
5. Technical developers within the ENVRI RIs or associated projects, especially in the data systems. They are included to gain understanding of the relevant policy requirements influencing their technical choices, and as a way to bring this policy information to user interfaces and the metadata for the data products.
6. EOSC Association and other international and regional communities, who are approached as users and stakeholders for these suggested policies.

The target audiences are focusing on Development (1), Approval (2), Implementation (3), and Alignment (4) of policies. The most important target audiences (1 and 2) – but also the other target audiences - are approached using ENVRI workshops.

1.3 How to use this document

This document creates a first iteration of the expected policy statements (defined in the next chapter), which each RI should consider. These statements are intended as the core of the actual policy documents, where the RI clearly states their positioning on the issues at hand. The document can thus be used for:

- RIs to analyse their own policy decisions in this framework and identify any developments needed.
- Project partners and RI specialists to analyse the feasibility of the suggested policy decisions, and to improve the existing framework to better match the requirements.
- EOSC related entities to understand the organisational changes needed in the RIs relating to the requirements from the EOSC.

It can also be used as the basis of planning actual policy development. We have tried to make the decisions from drivers to policy statements clear and transparent for application.

In addition, there are several areas where some caution should be exercised. Due to the draft state and continuously developing EOSC landscape, the analysis of the policy drivers might not be fully characterising the actual intent of the documents themselves. Furthermore, this document does not imply any clear internal practices (guidelines) or technical solutions (IT implementation) required for the implementation of the policies at the practical level in the RIs. Several additional policy statements might and most likely will be needed in each RI.

1.4 Definition and purpose of Research Infrastructure Policies

Why should we be interested in policies? What they are, and how do they differ from other parts of FAIR data service production, and of organization development in general?

The term “policy” has a variety of definitions and meanings in the literature (see e.g., D4.2 introduction) and is often context dependent. There is the need to define the term policy for the purposes of this deliverable, including the kind of policies being targeted, and how they differ from other organizational decisions.

Policies *in the context of this document* are **official decisions that describe the intended goals and principles behind some aspect of organizational functions**. The main purpose of any policy is to *communicate* the intent and long-term commitments of the RI to different communities (employees, stakeholders, and users). To achieve this, there are many aspects of policies which are crucial for their success, which are detailed more in the Appendix 4 of this deliverable. In general, these policies are used in the RIs for many different reasons, perhaps most important categories of these are:

- **Internal use:** *to direct the organization’s internal procedures and development, give motivation and guidance on required actions (behaviours) and to justify internally processes.* Here the targets are people working directly in the research infrastructures or via an agreement. This can be considered as *(co)development use* of policies.
- **External stakeholder use;** *to show compliance and strategic goals to external stakeholders (funding bodies, member organizations, certification authorities etc.).* This also includes adherence to EOSC Rules of Participation, (optionally) undertaking selected accreditation processes such as Core Trust Seal for certification of repositories, as well compliance with other authorities or organizations as well as international or national law. A key stakeholder group for many RIs within the ESFRI context are the national funding bodies, which have their own requirements for FAIR data delivery and other related aspects of open science. By having public policy decisions on this subject, the RIs demonstrate that these requirements are being considered as part of infrastructure operations. This can be considered an *upstream use* of policies.

- **Informing External clients(users);** *to demonstrate accessibility and interoperability to user communities* (e.g., domain and data scientists, service developers, Virtual Research Environments, external data searches, companies, etc.). This usage is particularly important in the case of users and access policies, but it can also be crucial for many other policies as well. A key aspect is to communicate to these communities via policy documents or metadata, what are the limitations and organizational decisions related to their use of infrastructure policies, which can be considered a *downstream use* of policies.

The ENVRI policy framework is built on data interoperability (commonly via services offered) and thus the majority of the policies studied are thus connected directly or indirectly to organizational aspects related to them. The results are intended to be generally applicable, and some level of abstractness is unavoidable. Thus, challenges emerge from trying to generalize policies, and to make them separable from the details specific to the organization of which they are part. To alleviate this issue, there is a need to model and define both the policy decisions and ENVRI RI organizations in an abstract way.

The ENVRI cluster of organizations needs to have policies to enable their collective objectives to be met. In addition, RI organizations within ENVRI need to have their own community specific policies. A major objective of Work Package (WP) 4 in ENVRI-FAIR is to reconcile any differences.

1.5 Policy Statements, Practices and Technological Solutions

To further define the way infrastructure policies are approached in this framework, we have thus developed a model to distinguish between internal and external parts of the policy decisions. The model consists of selecting the actual organizational processes involved in developing the infrastructure operations from external requirements to actual operational (and technical) solution providing the service. The model is partly based on the workshop responses of first ENVRI policy workshop (Oct. 2021).

The core of this model distinguishes three basic steps (plus one initial step) for the provision of data services inside the infrastructure from the decision making perspective that are:

- 0) **Policy driver** (prerequisite), which defines the external or internal reason for the policy to exist. This can usually be derived from strategy documents, high level principles, or (in this document) from the external requirements of bodies, such as where membership is crucial for the ENVRI RIs, e.g. European Open Science Cloud. Often it is useful to analyze such policy drivers to determine these specific **requirements**.
These drivers are often coming from outside the infrastructure organization (external regulatory bodies, General Assembly members, Members states, etc.), but their requirement analysis is commonly done inside the infrastructure management structures.
An example of this kind of requirement could be “*service providers must provide a unique identifier for each dataset they register for the service*”. These could be defined as the rationale for **why** the RI policy exists.
- 1) **Policy statement (PS)**, which succinctly defines the high-level policy decision answering to the policy driver, and clearly states the position of the organization on the issue. A policy statement is approved by an authority in the research infrastructure, and it is typically intended to have a long time-horizon of applicability. The statements are primarily intended for human readability, although can in some cases be coded for machine readability. Policy statements do not typically include direct guidance on which parts of an organization should carry out the required action required, or the technologies involved. They can and should be stated in a relatively RI-agnostic form (i.e. not referring to specificities of individual RIs). Often “policies” as discussed in many EOSC-related documents and other such initiatives, refer to these policy statements, and thus the Policy Framework is also mainly referring to them.

The policy statements are prepared by the research infrastructure, and as mentioned above, approved by an internal authority. They can be used on all three main use cases of the policy use. Commonly these policies are relatively short statements, e.g. “*All production data sets in*

this research infrastructures will have a persistent and unique identifier assigned". These statements can be viewed as **what** the organization should be doing to fulfil a specific policy driver.

- 2) **Practice description (PD)** Also known as guidelines, this part of policy implementation describes how the organization's own internal actions are enacting the policy statement. This can include details of operations, workflows, responsibilities, and rules, which specify the internal steps necessary to achieve the result required by the policy statement. A key part of this description is that it concentrates on an organization's internal activities, although can often include tasks intended as part of the responsibilities of an associated organisations (e.g., national nodes, data submitters, or research performing organizations). The time frame of practices is often shorter than policy statements due to potential changes in the organizational structures, needs and resources.

The practice descriptions are driven by policy statements, but also by internal drivers that have a role in their development (e.g. available expertise, resources, interests), as well as technological choices. They are also extremely RI-specific as they directly refer to the roles and positions inside the organization and are thus often not directly transferrable between RIs. However, some features can be generalised and (best) practices can and should be shared between them where possible.

These practice documents can have official authorization but are instead often more managerial or community-oriented in nature and can be developed in a common effort as less official practical documentation. The descriptions are typically in the form of a human readable static documents, wiki or living document, but in some cases, workflows could be also made machine readable (e.g., using descriptions from the ENVRI Reference Model). The practice descriptions commonly answer **who and how** in the organization is to fulfil the policy driver requirements. In the ENVRI Reference Model these aspects can sometimes be modelled in the Science Viewpoint.

- 3) **Technical solution (TS)** - usually an IT implementation. Describes the technologies and operational workflows from the perspective of the data and processing steps. These solutions are often highly specific in nature but can and should be based on commonly developed technical community standards and interfaces, especially for cross-RI interoperability. A large part of the ENVRI FAIR activities are connected to the TS of the ENVRI infrastructures, and this is also the major aspect of all technology-based developments in the EOSC and more generally, for open science practices.

Technical solution documentation often references technical data sheets, descriptions, etc., and even if they are intended for human readability, often come in a form requiring a high level of specialist knowledge of terminology and underlying technologies. In some cases, the technical documentation can be supported by automated compliance tools and the chosen technologies are often also described in the metadata for the services themselves. Due to rapid technological advances, technical solution(s) can often evolve quickly and have a relatively limited time span. However, the scale of investments and existing interoperability networks create some longevity for existing systems, even if more modern solutions already exist. Technological choices can also be driven by *techno-economic drivers*, rather than direct policy requirements, which creates its own challenges for when seeking to align necessary technical interoperability with organizational goals.

The technological solutions are rarely purely RI specific, although this can happen in some cases and, by their very nature, they have a high potential for interoperability.

TS answers the question "**with what**" in the context of answering to the Policy Driver. In the ENVRI Reference Model these aspects are connected to the Computational, Information and Technology Viewpoints.

These steps do not necessarily need to be in separate documents, and they do not always follow each other in a clear progression. Sometimes the policy drivers are not actually written, or formally referenced, and certain technologies have existed before they have found a suitable application to solve a specific policy driver. Furthermore, communities might have created practices without any formal policy decision and with many different technological solutions. It is also common practice to combine many of these aspects into the same documents within existing RI policy and best practice documentation.

2 Policy drivers and requirements

2.1 Policy drivers

Policies must be based on the practical needs or strategic goals of the Research Infrastructures, or their key stakeholders. In this document, we consider several key goals of (data related) policy development (with their related requirements), which are:

1. RIs can connect, and particularly supply data/services, to the **European Open Science Cloud** as a full and recognized participant. This is a major goal of the whole ENVRI-FAIR project, and the main consideration for this document. For this reason, the primary document for consideration is the **EOSC Rules of Participation**¹ (European Commission, 2021)

The RI data policies are largely consistent with the **FAIR principles**. This aspect is specifically mentioned in the ENVRI-FAIR project plan and is a major aspect of almost all ESFRI RI long-term open science related considerations. As consistency with FAIR principles is one of the key elements of the EOSC Rules of Participation, there are many similarities between the drivers resulting from these requirements and (1) above. However, interpretations of the FAIR principles vary and for those ENVRI RIs that are not immediately considering directly providing data/services to the EOSC, independent evaluation based on these principles could be useful. In this case, the original **FORCE11 FAIR principles**, and the derived **FAIR metrics** are key documents, together with their analysis (e.g., **D4.2** of ENVRI FAIR). It should be noted that this analysis is done in parallel with the FAIR Implementation Profiles developed in the ENVRI FAIR project and GO-FAIR, which provides a rich opportunity for further cross-analysis.

2. One of the key outcomes the ENVRI-FAIR project has been the start of the process to create the **ENVRI-Hub demonstrator**. This platform presents a potential opportunity for long-term interoperability and co-creation between the ENVRI RI products and the relevant user communities. Although the vision of the ENVRI-Hub is still being finalized at the time of drafting this document, the overall architecture and proposed functionalities create real requirements for the participating RIs. The main analysis of this development aspects are contained in the **ENVRI-HUB concept documents and internal development documents**.

2.2 Requirement analysis

The requirement analysis evaluates these policy drivers and considers their implications for the resulting RI policies and, if relevant, the associated practices and technological implementation. Analysis takes key sentences from the documents and tries to distil them into concrete infrastructure-relevant policy statements or requirements. In most cases this is relatively straightforward practice, but some cases require subjective analysis of the results and sometimes there are several optional ways to fulfil the policy requirement. Additional effort was invested to determine the priority of the requirement, i.e., how important the policy driver document considers the statement leading to the requirement. This priority was then used to evaluate the requirement and determines the language used in the policy statements. Figure 1 shows the overall decision tree for this activity.

¹ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, EOSC rules of participation, Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/30541>

Figure 1 Driver-statement-requirement analysis

These implications (requirements) can be divided in Primary requirements that directly respond to Drivers, Derived requirements that are derivatives from the Primary requirements (i.e., they are strict preconditions of Primary requirements), and some Optional requirements that are connected to Primary or Secondary requirements, but are either not strict preconditions, of low importance in the Driver documents, or seen as being optional for the RIs.

The analysis of each document is presented in Appendixes 1-3, with their relevant requirement or policy driver codes. In summary the requirements have been assigned codes as follows:

- The EOSC RoP document created a total of 37 partly overlapping requirements, which are indicated with the prefix **RROP**
- The FAIR principles created 19 requirements which are indicated with prefix **RFAIR**
- The ENVRI-Hub requirements are more limited, with only 3 operational requirements, indicated by prefix **RHUB**

3 Draft Policy Framework for EOSC and FAIR compliance (context of ENVRI infrastructures)

3.1 Policy statement template

As this framework is intended to be usable for the partner RIs, the policy statements included in this framework have a formal structure. They follow the following templates that include the necessary explanations:

Policy statement title:	<i>Short title of the policy</i>
Policy statement identifier:	<i>Internal identifier number (within this document)</i>
Example statement text:	<i>Policy statement in as short form as possible</i>
Description:	<i>Additional description of the statement, including references</i>

Policy requirements:	<i>Identifiers and explanation of the policy driver requirements related to the policy statement. This part can also include information about what could happen if the policy statement is not implemented.</i>
Policy connections:	<i>Connections to other policies, e.g. policy groupings, requirements for other policies and support for others.</i>
Application notes:	<i>Specific notes on applications where necessary, particularly on connected Practice and Technologies, and any options for other policies which could be used to answer the policy drivers.</i>

The policy statements are listed in broad categories, which can be used to, for example, group the policies together in specific policy documents.

3.2 Policy statements

This section lists the Policy Statements required to fulfil the Policy Drivers. They are generally categorized according to the main subject area, although many extend to cover several of these areas. **The categorisations do not imply any specific goal and are intended only for clarification. Many policy statements cover several category areas.** The policy statements are identified by a running index in each policy category. In future versions of this Policy Framework, newer versions of the Statements can be identified by including a version number in the identifier (e.g., “ENVRI-DATA-1.1”).

3.2.1 Data related policy statements (ENVRI-DATA)

Policy statement title:	Dataset PIDs
Policy statement identifier:	ENVRI-DATA-1
Example statement text:	Each production dataset has a globally unique persistent identifier assigned to it.
Description:	This policy refers to <i>production datasets</i> , which in this context mean datasets that are intended to be primarily used by research infrastructure user communities. This is in contrast to, e.g., raw data, or temporary data stages, although other policies can require their identification as well. The term <i>globally unique persistent identifier</i> refers to identifiers which reference only one specific dataset globally (i.e., across all infrastructures and repositories), and they are intended to be persistent (i.e., long-term), preferably lasting longer than the dataset storage sustainability plans.
Policy requirements:	RFAIR1, RFAIR2
Policy connections:	Requires: Dataset definitions (ENVRI-DATA-2), PID service provider (ENVRI-PID-1), Data provenance requirement (ENVRI-PROV-1), Long term commitment for PIDs (ENVRI-SUS-1)
Application notes:	Often this kind of PID is provided by an external service (e.g., DATACITE DOI), but can be also internal if the PID persistence and global uniqueness can be guaranteed.

Policy statement title:	Dataset type definitions
Policy statement identifier:	ENVRI-DATA-2
Example statement text:	Each production dataset type has a definition and scope, including a defined resolution (temporal, spatial and content).
Description:	This <i>dataset definition</i> is intended to standardize what the RI means by a “dataset” for each type of production dataset.
Policy requirements:	Required by ENVRI-DATA-1
Policy connections:	Required by ENVRI-DATA-1 as otherwise “dataset” is not defined.
Application notes:	Ideally these dataset types are exposed as a publicly available and citable reference, and each dataset should also include a reference to the type of definition used.

Policy statement title:	Data quality control
Policy statement identifier:	ENVRI-DATA-3
Example statement text:	Each production dataset type has documented quality indicators, and the dataset metadata includes this information
Description:	Data quality is indicated by some set of indicators necessary for the data user to evaluate its usefulness. The selection of these indicators depends on the dataset types and expected uses.
Policy requirements:	RROP16, RROP22
Policy connections:	Requires included metadata (ENVRI-META-1)
Application notes:	The application of this policy is highly domain specific, and quality can be investigated purely from technical point of view, or more holistically. The main goal should be on the expected usability of the data for its intended purpose.

3.2.2 Persistent Identifier (PID) policy statements (ENVRI-PID)

Policy statement title:	PID service provision
Policy statement identifier:	ENVRI-PID-1
Example statement text:	RI has a sustained solution for provision of globally persistent identifiers for digital objects
Description:	The RI needs PIDs, particularly for their datasets meant for production. This PID provision can be done internally or externally (via a PID provider) but needs to have a high level of longevity and sustainability to match requirements meant for PIDs. Global uniqueness is also required.
Policy requirements:	Derived
Policy connections:	Required by ENVRI-DATA-1, ENVRI-META-2
Application notes:	No specific provider is suggested, but practical application should consider using commonly used PID providers as they have potentially more suitable long term sustainability plan, and the PID usage can be potentially tracked in the future. Using commonly available PIDs is also easier for most user communities.

Policy statement title:	Resolving PIDs
Policy statement identifier:	ENVRI-PID-2
Example statement text:	Globally unique PIDs are sustainably and automatically resolvable to relevant (meta)data
Description:	This resolving can be done internally or externally but should be automatic and most importantly sustained even after the dataset is no longer available. This resolving system must work also in the case of change of dataset hosting service, etc.
Policy requirements:	RFAIR7
Policy connections:	ENVRI-META3 requirement
Application notes:	The result is often a landing page, with optional machine-to-machine interface. Practical mechanisms for longevity can be harder to ensure in internal applications.

3.2.3 Metadata related policy statements (ENVRI-META)

Policy statement title:	Data metadata requirement
Policy statement identifier:	ENVRI-META-1
Example statement text:	Each production dataset is accompanied or linked with detailed, rich, and documented metadata
Description:	The metadata included with the datasets must be relevant for their use, contain enough information to ensure potential re-use, evaluate data quality, and provide necessary provenance information.
Policy requirements:	RFAIR4, RFAIR15, RFAIR19, RROP-19
Policy connections:	Other META policies detail the required fields
Application notes:	The nature of “rich and documented” metadata can be considered as a major development goal

Policy statement title:	Metadata PIDs
Policy statement identifier:	ENVRI-META-2
Example statement text:	All metadata records related to production datasets have a globally unique PID
Description:	This policy refers to metadata for <i>production datasets</i> , which in this context mean datasets that are intended to be primarily used by research infrastructure user communities. The term <i>globally unique persistent identifier</i> refers to identifiers that reference only one dataset (i.e., across all infrastructures and repositories), which are intended to be persistent (i.e., long-term), preferably lasting longer than even the dataset storage sustainability plans.
Policy requirements:	RFAIR3, RFAIR2, RFAIR1
Policy connections:	ENVRI-DATA-1 is similar to data. Requires ENVRI-PID-1
Application notes:	Often this kind of PID is provided by an external service (e.g., DATACITE DOI), but can be also internal if the PID persistence and global uniqueness can be guaranteed.

Policy statement title:	Metadata links to dataset
Policy statement identifier:	ENVRI-META-3
Example statement text:	Metadata includes a clear qualified reference to the data they describe
Description:	Metadata records should always include a (resolvable) PID for the dataset described. In the case of a dataset that is no longer available, the link should be updated to a landing page describing the situation or the metadata record itself may indicate this situation.
Policy requirements:	RFAIR5
Policy connections:	Required by ENVRI-META-1
Application notes:	Detailed Practices should also consider the situation when a dataset storage location changes.

Policy statement title:	Metadata repository availability and searchability
Policy statement identifier:	ENVRI-META-4
Example statement text:	Metadata records for (production) datasets are registered or indexed in a searchable and openly available repository
Description:	The metadata records need to be openly available and searchable to ensure usability by the EOSC and other users. This can be done internally or externally (i.e., the repository can also be externally provided)
Policy requirements:	RFAIR6, RROP2, RROP3

Policy connections:	ENVRI-ACCESS-5 for metadata license
Application notes:	The existence of this kind of repository is necessary for any data producing RI, and sustainability and resilience of the repository application should be considered.

Policy statement title:	Metadata language and format
Policy statement identifier:	ENVRI-META-5
Example statement text:	Metadata use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation
Description:	<i>Formal</i> means that the metadata has a structured syntax and a semantically controlled vocabulary. <i>Accessible</i> means that the terms are as self-documenting as possible or are otherwise documented. <i>Shared</i> means that the documentation for the terms are widely available in the user community. <i>Broadly applicable</i> suggests the use of cross-disciplinary standards when possible
Policy requirements:	RFAIR13
Policy connections:	Addition to ENVRI-META-1. Requires ENVRI-META-6 for vocabularies
Application notes:	The creation or selection of the metadata format is complicated and often domain specific. Broad application suggests implementing widely used metadata schemas, and leveraging community efforts to include any RI specific terminology

Policy statement title:	Metadata vocabularies
Policy statement identifier:	ENVRI-META-6
Example statement text:	Metadata primarily uses controlled vocabularies. These vocabularies are available and support the FAIR principles
Description:	Metadata vocabularies are controlled sets of accepted terms for specified metadata fields. The requirement of FAIRness means, in practice, they should be accessible to a wide range of users and interoperable with other vocabularies
Policy requirements:	RFAIR14
Policy connections:	Required by ENVRI-META-5
Application notes:	Commonly such vocabularies are community efforts.

Policy statement title:	Service metadata
Policy statement identifier:	ENVRI-META-7
Example statement text:	Services provided to users must be documented with relevant and accurate metadata enabling their use, and an evaluation of their quality.
Description:	This documentation is critical for implementation in the EOSC platforms and should be done in collaboration with other ENVRI RIs.
Policy requirements:	RROP13, RROP16
Policy connections:	ENVRI-META-8 for FAIRness evaluation
Application notes:	Development of this service metadata is underway in the ENVRI FAIR catalogue of services task force.

Policy statement title:	Indication of FAIRness in the metadata
Policy statement identifier:	ENVRI-META-8
Example statement text:	Metadata should include a mechanism for the user to evaluate the FAIRness of the datasets or services
Description:	This need comes from EOSC requirements to ensure that the connected services (and data-services) have the necessary degree of FAIRness, and that this can be evaluated at the EOSC level.
Policy requirements:	RRPO8
Policy connections:	ENVRI-ACCESS-2 for access information, ENVRI-META-4 for findability, ENVRI-META-6 for vocabularies (re-usability)
Application notes:	This policy is difficult to fulfil unless relevant indicators can be identified. Some aspects, particularly Accessibility and Findability can be identified through licences and metadata standardization. Interoperability and reusability issues need to be further developed.

Policy statement title:	Metadata includes information on Terms of Use
Policy statement identifier:	ENVRI-META-9
Example statement text:	The metadata for services and data must include a reference to the Terms of Use and Licenses applicable
Description:	This element is critical for evaluating which services are usable at the EOSC level including specific limitations on use.
Policy requirements:	RROP26, RROP27
Policy connections:	Requires ENVRI-ACCESS-4 for licenses, ENVRI-ACCESS-6 for global open access, ENVRI-ACCESS-2 for access process documentation
Application notes:	The actual connectivity mechanisms are currently being developed in ENVRI FAIR Task Force 5.

Policy statement title:	Link to data origin
Policy statement identifier:	ENVRI-META-10
Example statement text:	Services using datasets maintain the link to data origin in their metadata or through other ancillary that is provided
Description:	This policy intends to formalize and underline the need to maintain authorship and original provenance of datasets (at least as references) even when combined with other datasets or transformed in a service.
Policy requirements:	RROP4
Policy connections:	Requires ENVRI-PROV-1
Application notes:	Usually included as a separate reference in the metadata schema

Policy statement title:	Provenance information
Policy statement identifier:	ENVRI-META-11
Example statement text:	Dataset and service metadata contains necessary information to evaluate the provenance and transformations applied to the original dataset(s). Earlier versions of the processed datasets are directly indicated via PIDs.
Description:	This kind of information needs to be included in all datasets to maintain their provenance and thus reliability. Important information includes transformation types (preferably with associated software PIDs), curators, operators, etc.
Policy requirements:	RROP33, RROP34
Policy connections:	Requires ENVRI-META-10, ENVRI-PROV-1
Application notes:	Common schema should be developed in the ENVRI community. At RI level this requires intensive service modelling, e.g., by using ENVRI Reference Model.

Policy statement title:	Acknowledgement information
Policy statement identifier:	ENVRI-META-12
Example statement text:	Metadata records must include recommended citation/ acknowledgement string and relevant PID.
Description:	This is needed to ensure correct referencing of the dataset
Policy requirements:	RROP30
Policy connections:	Requires ENVRI-DATA-1 for PIDs, ENVRI-
Application notes:	Common schema should be developed in ENVRI community. At RI level this requires intensive service modelling, e.g., using ENVRI Reference Model.

3.2.4 Sustainability and service upkeep policy statements (ENVRI-SUST)

Policy statement title:	Sustainability of PID links
Policy statement identifier:	ENVRI-SUST-1
Example statement text:	PIDs will resolve to relevant metadata even after the datasets are no longer available.
Description:	PID service providers (internal or external) and the metadata storage system must be chosen or built in a way which ensures their sustainability even if the datasets are no longer available, (even in the case of shutdown of the RI).
Policy requirements:	RFAIR11
Policy connections:	ENVRI-PID-1 for PID service selection, ENVRI-META-4 for metadata storage repository. Implies a policy for data deletion (ENVRI-SUST-2)
Application notes:	In practice this means that there should be some backup plan for the metadata storage even in the case of loss of primary data storage (e.g., infrastructure is terminated).

Policy statement title:	Data deletion policy
Policy statement identifier:	ENVRI-SUST-2
Example statement text:	RI develops and maintains a process for data deletion or reduction, including relevant changes to metadata if this is necessary.
Description:	This process should include issues such as prioritization, criteria for deletion/removal and what is done with the metadata records.
Policy requirements:	(Derived secondary)
Policy connections:	Implied by ENVRI-SUST-1
Application notes:	This policy is currently not often considered in ENVRI RIs but should be included. Reasons for deletion can be numerous, such as lack of resources, erroneous data, mistakes in data processing, intentional sabotage, or manipulation of datasets, etc. As a minimum such processes could be just referred as “no datasets will be deleted” and changed if needed.

Policy statement title:	Public access to policies
Policy statement identifier:	ENVRI-SUST-3
Example statement text:	Policy documents publicly available and linkable from the metadata
Description:	This visibility is important for the users and the EOSC to ensure that proper ethical, legal, and commonly accepted scientific processes are followed.
Policy requirements:	RROP18
Policy connections:	This is a “policy of policies” and more a general requirement for policy decisions
Application notes:	Also required by the recommended policy format (Appendix 4)

Policy statement title:	Liability evaluation
Policy statement identifier:	ENVRI-SUST-5
Example statement text:	Infrastructure service design must include considerations to limit liability for the RI
Description:	The service liability (including data quality issues, etc), should be considered by the RI, and, if needed, documented in the usage license.
Policy requirements:	RROP20
Policy connections:	ENVRI-ACCESS-4 for the data licence
Application notes:	This policy decision can require further evaluation from the Policy legal support Task

Policy statement title:	Licensing rights
Policy statement identifier:	ENVRI-SUST-6
Example statement text:	RI must have a right to license the production datasets for further use.
Description:	The data licenses assume that the RI has a right to license (and thus share) the production datasets. This must be ensured by written contracts or some other legal documentation.
Policy requirements:	RROP24
Policy connections:	Implied by ENVRI-ACCESS-4 and ENVRI-ACCESS-5
Application notes:	In most cases, this should be a part of the contracts for being part of / asset supplier to the RI, but special care should be taken where RIs allow user-uploaded datasets.

Policy statement title:	Legal compliance and privacy
Policy statement identifier:	ENVRI-SUST-7
Example statement text:	RI must comply to relevant regulations and scientific practices related to authorship and privacy within their metadata fields
Description:	This is a catchall policy determining the need to confirm that authorship and inclusion of personal information is done in a controlled fashion with appropriate permissions from the individual whose personal data is recorded.
Policy requirements:	RROP23
Policy connections:	Requires ENVRI-META-11 (provenance) and ENVRI-SUST-4 for ownership information
Application notes:	This policy statement requires additional considerations from the Task 4.4 in WP4.

3.2.5 Access policy statements (ENVRI-ACCESS)

Policy statement title:	Technical access protocols
Policy statement identifier:	ENVRI-ACCESS-1
Example statement text:	Metadata and data technical access follows commonly accepted protocols
Description:	These “commonly accepted protocols” are not defined here, but the policy statement specifies that no ad-hoc solutions should be used if possible. Standard internet protocols are generally used at the most basic level.
Policy requirements:	RFAIR8
Policy connections:	Indirectly provides for most META and ACCESS policies
Application notes:	Should be defined in collaboration with other RIs to maintain interoperability

Policy statement title:	Access process documentation
Policy statement identifier:	ENVRI-ACCESS-2
Example statement text:	For datasets requiring authorization procedures, the process is documented, and transparent and widely available
Description:	These authorization procedures should be clearly documented, the process should be transparent, and the users should be able to follow the criteria (and if denied, have a mechanism for requesting corrective actions)
Policy requirements:	RROP9
Policy connections:	Connected to ENVRI-ACCESS-3 for federated access requests, ENVRI-META-10 for inclusion of Terms of Use (e.g., licence) in metadata
Application notes:	Practices to gain access must be well documented and efficient inside the RI (particularly if requiring human intervention)

Policy statement title:	EOSC federated access
Policy statement identifier:	ENVRI-ACCESS-3
Example statement text:	Access to authorized users can be obtained via a trusted federated system
Description:	This especially refers to the EOSC exposed data services, which are required to use some sort of shared AAI provision.
Policy requirements:	RROP-11, RROP-25
Policy connections:	Requires ENVRI-ACCESS-2 for process to gain access
Application notes:	Application is developed within the ENVRI FAIR

Policy statement title:	Data licence(s)
Policy statement identifier:	ENVRI-ACCESS-4
Example statement text:	Production datasets have a suitable license, and this documentation is to be included in the linked metadata.
Description:	(Production) data should be licensed. The license must also be linked and documented in the metadata itself in a usable manner.
Policy requirements:	RFAIR16, RROP7, RROP21
Policy connections:	ENVRI-ACCESS-5 for metadata licences, ENVRI-SUST-6 for right to licence further.
Application notes:	Generally, an open license is recommended (see ENVRI-ACCESS-6 & RROP21), and a preferred community standard is most useful as the terms are clearer for user communities, especially in machine-to-machine environments

Policy statement title:	Metadata license(s)
Policy statement identifier:	ENVRI-ACCESS-5
Example statement text:	Metadata records have a suitable license which is documented accordingly.
Description:	Metadata should be licensed as they are created by individuals and shared and used for many purposes. The license must also be linked and documented in the metadata itself in a usable manner.
Policy requirements:	RFAIR17, RROP5
Policy connections:	Connected to ENVRI-ACCESS-4 (for data). Required by ENVRI-META-4
Application notes:	Generally, an open license is recommended (see ENVRI-ACCESS-6), and a preferred community standard is most useful as the terms are clearer for the user communities, especially in machine-to-machine environments.

Policy statement title:	Default open access
Policy statement identifier:	ENVRI-ACCESS-6
Example statement text:	Open (non-restricted) access is the default access mode for production datasets, and decisions otherwise need to be justified accordingly
Description:	Closed access is possible but must be necessary and separately justified.
Policy requirements:	RROP4
Policy connections:	Should be considered in ENVRI-ACCESS-4 selection
Application notes:	Practice to have closed datasets should be well documented and transparently accountable.

Policy statement title:	Global accessibility
Policy statement identifier:	ENVRI-ACCESS-7
Example statement text:	The services open to EOSC are intended to be available to all users, regardless of their origin
Description:	This means that RI services open to EOSC should not have geographical limitations, this does not imply that all services should follow this criterion.
Policy requirements:	RROP1
Policy connections:	ENVRI-ACCESS-2 for data requiring authorization, but that cannot be based on geographical origin for services open to EOSC.
Application notes:	This can be challenging for some ENVRI RIs, who can have limitations for non-member countries.

3.2.6 Provenance policy statements (ENVRI-PROV)

Policy statement title:	Infrastructure provenance information
Policy statement identifier:	ENVRI-PROV-1
Example statement text:	RI maintains an information repository which contains information on origin and all transformations done to each dataset, with relevant PID references.
Description:	This information should contain information on authorship and ownership, as well as direct links to PIDs for software used
Policy requirements:	RROP31, RROP32, RROP33, RROP34
Policy connections:	Requires ENVRI-DATA-2 for dataset definition
Application notes:	This requires careful consideration of the RI operations, and personnel involved. Modelling e.g. via ENVRI Reference model is recommended.

4 Intermediate Conclusions and Subsequent Steps

The policy (statement) framework (above) presented here is intended as the starting point for discussion and refinement within the ENVRI cluster of RIs.

The key analysis points to be discussed in the wider RI environment are:

- 1) Are the drivers relevant for the RIs involved? If, for example, the RI does not want to submit its services for the ENVRI-Hub demonstrator the requirements involving that driver are not relevant. Similar consideration can be made for both the FAIR principles and EOSC RoP.
- 2) Is the policy requirement analysis done correctly? The current version is based on relatively conservative and dogmatic reading of the EOSC RoP, and some aspects of the FAIR principles are a subject of interpretation. Additionally, even some level of prioritization was considered, but the actual level of requirements is presented in a flat structure – i.e., all requirements are considered equal in the framework. Additional work on the requirement analysis and prioritization is expected (and later fulfilled).
- 3) Are the requirements fulfilled by the policy statements? Or are the policy statements suggested too comprehensive for minimal fulfilment? The suggested and derived statements are based on subjective analysis and require community feedback.
- 4) Can the policy statements be realistically implemented in the ENVRI RIs? This means both organisational realism (e.g., are the organisations willing to do this) and are there enough practical and technological solutions to actually implement the policy statements in practice.

Many of these aspects were considered in the ENVRI FAIR 2nd Policy Workshop, which took place on 8th of February 2022. In general, the framework was recognised and agreed by the RIs, and the next step is to move forward and develop the required policy documents, guidelines (practice) and IT implementations (technical).

This is being achieved by proposing a methodology that uses the existing EPOS Policy Group activities as an example. This is not to suggest adopting the EPOS documents but rather to stimulate the RIs to consider their own policy environments and how to evolve towards interoperability across the ENVRI RIs and ENVRI-Hub. This approach involves going from the Policy Statements to Policies, from Policies to Guidelines, and from Guidelines to IT Implementation.

5 From Policy Statements to Policies

The policy statements above provide a reasonably comprehensive basis for constructing policies. However, deeper analysis indicates some deficiencies:

- (1) There is no mention of how to deal with cookies.
- (2) Liability is mentioned (under sustainability) but its relationship to Terms and Conditions (T&C) is generally unclear, although mentioned with respect to the T&C for conditions of use of EOSC, namely SROP7, SROP28.
- (3) More generally, Terms and Conditions are not mentioned in the context of policies.
- (4) The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR²) is also only mentioned in the context of EOSC conditions, namely SROP23, yet has much wider application (and legal consequences) throughout the ENVRI cluster with regards to a policy on personal privacy.
- (5) The e-Privacy Directive³ of the European Commission is not mentioned.
- (6) There is no mention of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)⁴ or ethical research in general.

These deficiencies are serious, pervasive and have potential consequences if not addressed. Thus, the policy environment for ENVRI has been re-drawn to take account the wider context (Figure 3) to ensure that the policies take into account the constraints under which RIs operate (e.g., agreements with other organisations). The diagram illustrates the sources of these constraints.

² <https://gdpr-info.eu/>

³ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/eprivacy-regulation>

⁴ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/ee9bacdf-fdad-46eb-8cd8-32879e310191/language-en>

More importantly, it was necessary to define policies that are out of scope for the present objective as defined in this deliverable [Appendix 6] and those in scope [Appendix 7] in order to concentrate the work effort on the policy areas of most relevance to the objectives of ENVRI-FAIR.

Figure 3 The wider context of ENVRI Policy.

For these reasons, it was decided:

- (a) to take the policy statements and utilise them in constructing a set of policies (one policy per policy area) to meet the requirements of ENVRI, considering EOSC, FAIR and ENVRI-Hub requirements and constraints as outlined in previous sections but
- (b) broadening to encompass the wider framework of legislation and directives (national, regional, international) such as GDPR and e-Privacy, and the basis of a contract or agreement between users, asset suppliers and IT system providers in the context of Terms and Conditions.

As was noted in section 3.3, there are quite complex interactions between the policy areas. To overcome this complexity, at least to some degree, and to accommodate the policy aspects missing from the initial policy statement work, a new set of policy areas was defined as follows [Appendix 7]:

Physical Security
Disaster Recovery
Privacy
Authentication
Authorisation
Terms and Conditions
Cookies
Metadata
Identifiers
Licensing
Curation
Provenance
Quality Assurance
Acknowledgement
Responsible Research and Innovation

This set of policy areas covers all those from the previous categorisation and extends to cover the previously missing aspects. Furthermore, it provides the possibility of tracing back from specific guidelines to the supporting policies, thus providing a governance responsibility chain from the IT implementation back through guidelines to policies.

It is expected that ENVRI RIs will work towards having a set of policies covering these policy areas, using the framework of policy statements outlined in Section (3) but with the addition of the aspects discussed above in section (5). The third ENVRI Policy Workshop aimed at supporting this and provided the RI representatives attending with the information and processes to achieve a cohesive set of policies.

6 From Policies to Guidelines (Practices)

There is a many-to-many (n:m) relationship between policies, guidelines and IT implementation as illustrated in (Figure 4).

Policies, Guidelines and Implementation

Figure 4 Policies, guidelines, and IT implementation.

The key areas for guidelines covering the practicalities faced by a RI (and by ENVRI-Hub) in provision of systems to satisfy their users are the provision of assets, access to assets, privacy, security and Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI). As with policies, there are intersections and interdependencies between guidelines, but each guideline is intended to express clearly what should be done in each business procedure to respect the policies of the organisation. The guidelines are:

Asset Provision Data
Asset Provision Services
Asset Provision Software
Asset Provision Documentation
Asset Provision Publication
Asset Access Data
Asset Access Services
Asset Access Software
Asset Access Documentation
Asset Access Publication
Personal Data Privacy

Security: Physical Security
Security: Disaster Recovery
Security: Authentication
Security: Authorisation
RRI

It is expected that ENVRI RIs will work towards having a set of guidelines covering these areas using the policy statements developed as described in section (5). The third ENVRI Policy Workshop is aimed at initiating support for this objective.

7 From Guidelines to IT Implementation (Technological Solutions)

Using the example of the European Plate Observing System (EPOS) RI (Figure 5), the IT implementation of policy and guidelines requires provision for both the human user (or their IT agent) on the left, and the digital assets such as services, datasets, data products, software, workflows, equipment, facilities..) on the right. The relationship between the user and the asset is managed by policies in the centre of the diagram.

How it all links together (EPOS example)

Figure 5 IT Implementation.

This (IT implementation to support policies) will be addressed subsequently, once ENVRI RIs have policy documents and guidelines.

7.1 Workshop 3

A workshop was held on 30 November 2022 with the objectives of:

- Presenting the approach that has been re-orientated towards developing policies (policy documents), guidelines and IT implementation on the basis of the identified policy statements.
- Discussing the approach with examples and evaluate their relationship to existing and planned future policy environments in the RIs considering all the requirements including interoperation in ENVRI and EOSC and conformance to existing best practices.
- Evaluating the approach for developing the policy environment for the ENVRI-Hub taking into account all the requirements including interoperation in ENVRI and EOSC.

- (d) Agreeing future actions within each RI and the ENVRI-Hub to put in place appropriate policy environments to be documented in deliverable D4.7.

The conclusions of the workshop define the pathway through D4.6 (this deliverable) to D4.7 (the final policy deliverable) which itself is to be generated from the outputs of workshop 4 that will take place in February 2023.

8 The three key Policies and their implementation

During Workshop 3 the need to implement three key policies that are regarded as essential and urgent for all ENVRI RIs (and ENVRI-Hub) was also discussed. These policies are necessary to protect the organisation and ensure compliance with relevant laws and directives. These are:

1. Privacy (Personal Data Privacy) because there are strong penalties for infringement.
2. Terms and Conditions because an agreement is made between the user and the organization owning the system.
3. Cookies because Europe (and other regions) require that users can choose which cookies to allow.

The key to implementation is to obtain user consent. This requires appropriate buttons for the user to click and to obtain a brief explanation and link to the corresponding policy document. The consent form used in EPOS that has been used as an exemplar is illustrated in Figure 6 below.

User Consent

EPOS POLICIES

I consent to Terms and Conditions
Here you will find the conditions under which you use the EPOS ICS-C portal. This includes acceptable use and liability disclaimer. If you do not consent to such use of the portal, further access to the portal is denied.

I understand and acknowledge the Privacy Policy document
The Privacy policy explains how EPOS-ERIC manages and protects personal data, particularly in the sense of GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation). If you do not consent to such use of your personal data, further access to the portal is denied.

COOKIES
Websites utilise cookies to store certain information. EPOS-ERIC ICS-C portal uses cookies only to monitor performance anonymously, information used in improving the portal. You may choose to allow these cookies or not. Either choice does not prevent use of the portal.

Figure 6 User Consent pop-up form

The policy documents themselves, indicated by the document symbol anchors in the consent pop-up form above, are at:

- https://www.epos-eu.org/sites/default/files/Privacy_Policy.pdf
https://www.epos-eu.org/sites/default/files/Terms_and_Conditions.pdf
https://www.epos-eu.org/sites/default/files/Cookie_Policy.pdf

The essential content of each of the three policies is illustrated in Figure 7s 7, 8, and 9 below which use the current content of the EPOS policies as example implementations.

Privacy (relates to GDPR)

<https://www.epos-eu.org/epos-eric-privacy-policy>

- Information about us and this policy
- Information we may collect about you
- Your legal rights
- Glossary

- Policy
- Data Controller
- DPO contact details

- Categories of personal data
- How is your personal data collected?
- How we use your personal data
- Communications
- Cookies
- International transfers
- Data security
- Data retention

Figure 7 Privacy Policy Essentials

Terms and Conditions

https://www.epos-eu.org/sites/default/files/Terms_and_Conditions.pdf

Your responsibility
 By using our Portal, you accept these terms.
 You must keep your account details safe

We may change the Portal
 We may make changes to these terms
 We may make changes to our Portal
 We may suspend or withdraw our Portal
 We may transfer this agreement to someone else

Use of material on Portal
 How you may use material on our Portal....
 Permitted uses
 Do not rely on information on our Portal
 We are not responsible for Portals we link to
 Rules about linking to our Portal.

Breach of these Terms
 Which country's laws apply to any disputes

EPOS ICS-C Terms and Conditions If you disagree with any part of these terms and conditions, please do not use our website.
 By accepting these Terms and Conditions, you enter into an agreement with EPOS ERIC, an international organisation with registered offices at EPOS ERIC, in Via di Vigna Murata 605 - 00143 Rome Italy - FISCAL CODE 96409510581 - VAT N° IT15152381008 ("EPOS ERIC "), made up by the contents of these Terms, in order to regulate the user's access and use of the Portal.

Figure 8 Terms and Conditions Essentials

Figure 9 Cookies Essentials

9 Policies Related to ENVRI-Hub

In parallel with assisting RIs to share best practice and develop policies, guidelines and IT implementations, it is also necessary to develop a similar policy environment for the ENVRI-Hub. The ENVRI-Hub catalogue contains rich, graph-structured metadata records describing RI digital assets in such a way as to make them discoverable, contextualizable, accessible, interoperable, and re-usable. However, different RIs can supply metadata records of varying levels of richness, but the basic principle is that RIs expose the assets that they make available to the ENVRI community (and beyond) through metadata records that include the conditions of use of those assets, which is the part relating to policy. The aim is maximum compatibility between the policies of the ENVRI-Hub and those of the ENVRI RIs (and their asset suppliers) to reduce friction and increase interoperability.

9.1 ENVRI Catalogue

The proposed policies for the ENVRI-Hub catalogue are presented in Figure 10 below.

Policies Related to ENVRI Catalog

- Most policies concerned with: (a) the rights and responsibilities of humans; (b) the rights and protection of digital assets; (c) the interaction between (a) and (b)
- The purposes of the catalog related to policy:
 - Curation (Availability of digital assets and FAIR)
 - Security (protection of digital assets)
 - Privacy (personal data)
 - Authorisation of access (protection of digital assets and recording for provenance, citation and usage requires authentication)
 - Licensing (protection of digital assets name of licence and authorisation parameters)
 - Provenance (tracking of asset evolution and use for privacy)
 - Citation (tracking for accreditation of researcher)
 - Usage tracking (for statistics indicating popularity and usage of personal data)

The catalog

- Metadata: representation of policy elements: syntax and semantics, integrity
- API
- GUI / query interface

How well does the catalog support policy?

- Sufficient information in the metadata, consistency
- Sufficient processes/procedures (IT implementation) utilising the metadata to support/enforce policy as defined in guidelines

The catalog provides a mechanism for TECHNICAL interoperability. However, we also need interoperability of IT implementations based on conforming policies and guidelines

Figure 10 Policies Relating to ENVRI-Hub Catalogue

9.2 Interoperability and Conformance

The policies (a subset of those for the ENVRI-Hub) needed for interoperation are presented in Figure 11, where the centre column of the figure expands upon the policies named on the left indicating where (in what processes or services) the policies are applied. The key point is to achieve sufficient compatibility for interoperation.

POLICY Interoperation

How do we achieve this in ENVRI: ENVRI -Hub / RI -RI / interface to EOSC

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Terms and Conditions Cookies Privacy Authentication Authorisation Metadata (FAIR) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Curation Provenance Licensing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Acknowledgement Citation 	<p>T&C: Liability, respect terms</p> <p>Cookies: For certain functions (maintaining state) and collecting usage data</p> <p>Privacy: GDPR conformance</p> <p>Authentication: Valid user</p> <p>Authorisation: Permission to access asset in appropriate modality</p> <p>Metadata: discovery, contextualization, workflow orchestration including curation and provenance</p> <p>Licensing: usage conditions, attribution/citation/acknowledgement</p>	<p>All Require SUFFICIENT conformity for interoperation</p>
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Figure 11 Policies Relating to Interoperation

The way forward for discussion on the combination of conformance (between ENVRI-Hub and RIs/asset suppliers) and policy interoperation is presented in Figure 12. This is the subject of Workshop 4.

Policy Interoperation / Conformance

- To be discussed when a quorum of RIs have their policies, guidelines and IT implementations defined
- A new landscape analysis at that time to identify any nonconformances / inconsistencies with the recommendations of the WP5 TFs and individual RI governance
- A plan to finalise evolutionary convergence of policies of ENVRI RIs, ENVRHub and EOSC

These are the next steps

ENVRI

Figure 12 Conformance and Interoperation

10 The Way Forward: Next Steps

10.1 Policies for the ENVRI-Hub and ENVRI RIs

ENVRI-Hub provides, among other features, user- and API-access to the catalogue of digital assets that ENVRI RIs expose at ENVRI-Hub. User access (or by software on behalf of users) to that catalogue is governed by policies that are implemented through guidelines and IT solutions.

In principle, the RIs choose the way and under what conditions they expose their digital assets to the ENVRI-Hub community (and, by implication, the EOSC community) which is implemented through the exporting (or harvesting) of metadata from their RI catalogue into the ENVRI-Hub catalogue.

It is therefore necessary for the ENVRI-Hub to have policies, guidelines, and an IT implementation in much the same way as any of the ENVRI RIs. However, RIs may decide to apply different conditions for access to their metadata in the ENVRI-Hub than for their metadata in the local RI catalogue. Ideally, such conditions would be recorded in the metadata (e.g., by licence conditions) which is also the aim within ENVRI-FAIR. In addition, the overarching policies concerning privacy, T&C and cookies need to be in place with appropriate acknowledgement/consent.

The key policies are (Figure 10):

- (a) Curation: Availability of digital assets) and FAIR
- (b) Security (protection of digital assets)
- (c) Privacy (personal data)
- (d) Authorisation of access (protection of digital assets and recording for provenance, citation and usage requires authentication)
- (e) Licensing (protection of digital assets: name of licence and authorisation parameters)
- (f) Provenance: (tracking of asset evolution and use for privacy)
- (g) Citation (tracking for accreditation of researcher)
- (h) Usage tracking (for statistics indicating popularity and usage of personal data)

10.2 Implementation

Implementation of policies, guidelines and their IT supporting mechanisms has two aspects: (1) implementation within the RIs and asset suppliers; (2) implementation in the ENVRI-Hub. The former is the business of the RIs and asset suppliers, but their policies must be compatible with those of ENVRI-Hub if they are to upload metadata describing their digital assets through the technical interoperation architecture. The latter requires agreement among all the ENVRI RIs. Policy workshops 2 and 3 have laid the groundwork for this implementation, while workshop 4 aims reach a consensus on how we achieve conformant policies for interoperation among RIs and ENVRI-Hub and onward to EOSC.

Appendix 1. Requirement analysis for EOSC Rules of Participation

Document overview: Published in 2020, this document summarizes the work of the *EOSC Executive Board Rules of Participation (RoP) Working Group (WG)*, in a relatively concise form. The document “state the standards and conduct required of EOSC participants⁵” and “EOSC participants agree to adhere to the RoP.”, it is assumed that it refers to any organization or individual using the platform, particularly as a service provider. This makes the document extremely important for the ENVRI RIs intending to use the EOSC platform for their own purposes. The document states the following key high-level rules, with relevant commentaries:

- **EOSC is based on the principle of openness**
- **EOSC resources align with FAIR principles**
- **EOSC services align with EOSC architecture & interoperability guidelines**
- **EOSC is based on principles of ethical behaviour and research integrity**
- **EOSC users are expected to contribute to EOSC**
- **EOSC users adhere to terms and conditions associated with the resources they use**
- **EOSC users reference the resources they use in their work**
- **Participation in EOSC is subject to applicable policies and legislation**

There are many general statements on the overall intent of the document and its use: The RoP is intended to be further developed in the future and refers to itself as “aspirational”. It is now (late 2021) being further developed in the EOSC Association working groups⁶. In practice, this means that some of the details of the RoP might vary in the future, demanding changes in the associated policies. However, no major changes for the principles themselves seem to be expected. The RoP apply to all EOSC Participants (i.e. including the participating RIs) and are also not only applicable to data and services, but also for other research assets such as publications, software, tools, workflows, training and consultancy. They also apply to all resources provided or accessed via the EOSC.

The RoP requirements are intentionally as short and terse as possible, which creates some issues of interpretation for the purposes of our analysis, and most of the requirements are derived from the adjoining commentaries, which are considered to be a part of the RoP.

Statement reference no	Statement	Requirement text	Requirement reference no
SROP1	Use of EOSC is open to anyone, regardless of role or geography. However, the EOSC is envisaged primarily for use by researchers in Europe and beyond.	RI resources intended for EOSC are available for all users, regardless of their geographical origin.	RROP1

⁵ The document uses draft EOSC glossary terms to define “participant”, “user”, “resource”, etc. using *draft EOSC Glossary* (https://docs.google.com/document/d/1rA3XNw-ORrDzBUyZwOolacTOOBpjOaxWmFdg_EEZcpA/edit)

⁶ European Commission, *EOSC Rules of Participation, Report from the EOSC Executive Board Rules of Participation (RoP) Working Group (WG)*, Edited by EOSC Rules of Participation Working Group, doi: 10.2777/30541, 2021

SROP2	EOSC resources are listed in a publicly accessible registry, comply with policy requirements (for example on openness of publicly funded data) and are findable without charge by all users.	RI resources intended for EOSC are listed in a publicly available registry, which is findable and freely available to all users (no charge).	RROP2
SROP3	Terms of use must be made available by resource providers, including information about whether access requires authentication and authorisation; licencing; and any quotas or charges which may apply.	Terms of use (including Authentication, authorization, licencing, quotas, charges) must be made publicly available in the registry.	RROP3
SROP4	Open access is the default and any departure from this must be justified.	Open access is default access mode for RI products, departure is always justified.	RROP4
SROP5	Resources that are open will be tagged as such so that they can be easily found among the EOSC resources.	Open access is clearly stated in the resource metadata.	RROP5
SROP6	Data in EOSC should be made available in accordance with FAIR principles, the requirements of which extend to all EOSC resources as data may require software and other resources to yield reproducible research.	Data and other resources must be made available in accordance to FAIR principles.	RROP6
SROP7	Individual research objects, such as datasets, publications, software, etc., or repositories of research objects, that are findable via the EOSC may have specific terms and conditions associated with them. However, these must comply with the EOSC FAIR principles. Examples of such conditions include licensing, or legal and ethical conditions on how data can be utilised.	Use conditions must be made clear in the metadata.	RROP7
SROP8	EOSC FAIR principles shall be applied so that a potential data re-user can assess the FAIRness of the data under consideration.	(meta)data must include a way to assess FAIRness of the data products.	RROP8
SROP9	Openness of processes and responsibilities, together with transparency of decision making, is to be expected.	Decision making and processes related to (EOSC) service provision need to be transparent and open.	RROP9
SROP10	EOSC architecture and interoperability guidelines shall enable user environments to be built across EOSC resources for enriching the user experience.	User created environment use of RI products should be allowed.	RROP10

SROP11	services requiring authentication or authorisation should support the use of relevant credentials for federated AAI as defined by the EOSC AAI taskforce.	Data access via federated AAI should be allowed.	RROP11
SROP12	Where access requires authentication and/or authorisation, data providers should make clear what body will make these decisions (e.g., Data Access Committee) along with appropriate details-	Data access procedure should be transparent.	RROP12
SROP13	Services shall be described by a commonly agreed metadata scheme.	Service metadata should follow a (selected) common scheme.	RROP13
SROP14	Service providers shall define and publish the terms of use for their services, including, for example, licensing, authentication and authorisation requirements, and any cost implications.	Terms of use are transparently available (including Licensing, authorization / access requirements, costs).	RROP14
SROP15	terms of use must comply with the EOSC principles and any relevant legal and ethical conditions on how data can be accessed, processed, analysed, changed and redistributed by others.	Service access comply with EOSC principles and relevant legal and ethical conditions related to access, processing, analysis, changes, and redistribution.	RROP15
SROP16	Service providers define and publish their own quality targets for their services such as through a Service Level Specification or Service Level Agreement, and agree that the EOSC-Core may monitor and report on the service levels achieved by an EOSC service	Service (data, metadata) quality targets are defined and published.	RROP16
SROP17	EOSC users and providers will act in accordance with commonly agreed principles regarding the conduct of research.	RI provision is in accordance with commonly agreed principles regarding conduct of research.	RROP18
SROP18	Resource providers agree not to wilfully misrepresent resources or provide false information.	Metadata is accurate and presents the data and services as faithfully as practically possible.	RROP19
SROP19	It is expected that the liability of the EOSC services for misconduct will be regulated in the individual contracts between the EOSC association and the service provider.	(derived) Liability of service and (meta)data provision must be considered in the RI.	RROP20
SROP20	Wherever possible, the use of open content and open software licenses for EOSC resources is required.	Open licences are used for services, data, and metadata	RROP21

SROP22	Resource providers define and publish quality targets for their services, and agree that the EOSC may monitor and report on the level of usage of their resource through EOSC.	Services (including Data services) have defined and published quality targets (with relevant metrics), which can be monitored. These can be shared to EOSC for relevant services.	RROP22
SROP23	Any data collected on contributions to and use of EOSC will be handled in accordance with relevant legislation and guidelines on data protection and privacy including GDPR.	Data and metadata maintained and shared by the RI fulfil the relevant legislation and guidelines on data protection and privacy, including GDPR.	RROP23
SROP24	Ownership of resources is not changed when they are made available through EOSC.	Ownership of resources should be made clear and documented.	RROP24
SROP25	EOSC users agree to adhere to the terms of use for the specific resources they use.	Terms of use can be agreed in the EOSC level or are easily done before service use.	RROP25
SROP26	The implication is that whilst service providers define and publish the terms of use for the service, they are provisioning, these terms are themselves consistent with the EOSC RoP.	Terms of use for resources are published, as are the EOSC RoP compliance.	RROP26
SROP27	Includes licensing and conditions of use, and whether access requires authentication and/or authorisation.	Resource metadata includes licences and conditions of use, and whether there is a need for authentication and authorisation.	RROP27
SROP28	Access to some resources may explicitly require users to accept Terms & Conditions before access is granted.	If agreement to terms and conditions agreement is needed, the relevant EOSC services providing access to the product can pass this agreement.	RROP28
SROP29	Resource providers have to indicate, perhaps through checkboxes, the conformity of their data and services with the standards and regulations. The resources are not accessible through EOSC until these checkboxes are filled.	(UNCLEAR)⁷	RROP29

⁷ This requirement in the EOSC RoP is unclear, and can be included in the future versions of this Framework. The numbering is kept, but RROP29 is not referenced further. Analysis suggests that this is more directed towards “casual” or “non-institutional” service providers.

SROP30	Examples of conditions that resource providers may require include: acknowledgement of the intellectual work of original creators and, where the resource stipulates, use of a standard form for this acknowledgment; or agreement to adhere to and not wilfully violate any terms of use associated with the resource.	Resource is recommended to include standard acknowledgement text.	RROP30
SROP31	Data providers offer users the appropriate references to their raw or processed data, preferably as PIDs.	Metadata contains references to raw or unprocessed data (preferably via PID).	RROP31
SROP32	Transparency in tracing back the origin, authors, and/or curators of datasets in the research data cycle.	Data origin and authors, and curators are maintained in the metadata in transformations.	RROP32
SROP33	Referencing all successive data transformations in the metadata using PIDs where available.	Each data transformation in the RI has a reference to previous version (preferably via PID).	RROP33
SROP34	The EOSC operators will offer guidance and technical support for constructing the metadata and PIDs showing the cascade of previous data transformations and the involved operators.	Resource metadata includes information of previous data transformations and operators.	RROP34
SROP35	The provision of rich (metadata) references will assist data providers and data processors in keeping account of the use of their data publications through EOSC.	Resource metadata refers to data origin.	RROP35
SROP36	EOSC operators will also provide a means to reference not only the resource used but also EOSC itself.	The EOSC accessible resources can be referenced via EOSC systems (i.e. reference information exists).	RROP36
		EOSC accessible resources can also have EOSC reference in addition to RI reference.	RROP37

Appendix 2. Requirement Analysis of FAIR Principles

This analysis used as the basis the original FORCE11 FAIR principles⁸, as well as GOFAIR commentaries on them (<https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>). In most cases, the actual FAIR text was directly implementable as a policy statement. A helpful interpretation is provided by Wilkinson et al⁹.

Statement reference no	Statement	Requirement text	Requirement reference no
F1	(Meta) data are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers.	(Production) Data(sets) must have a globally unique identifier.	RFAIR1
		(Production) Data(sets) must have a persistent identifier.	RFAIR2
		Metadata must have a PID.	RFAIR3
F2	Data are described with rich metadata.	(Production) Data(sets) must have rich metadata description.	RFAIR4
F3	Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data they describe.	Metadata associated with (Production) Data(sets) have an explicit identifier to the data(set).	RFAIR5
F4	(Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource.	Metadata associated with (Production) Data(sets) are indexed in a searchable resource.	RFAIR6
A1	(Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communication protocol.	Identifiers for data and metadata must be implemented in a way that they enable retrieval of (meta)data.	RFAIR7
A1.1	The protocol is open, free, and universally implementable.	Metadata and data access follows commonly accepted protocols.	RFAIR8
A1.2	The protocol allows for an authentication and authorisation where necessary.	If data or services requires authentication and authorization, the terms and methods must be made clear to users	RFAIR9

⁹ Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. *et al.* The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

		If data or services requires authentication, the access implementation must allow federated (EOSC) access protocol.	RFAIR10
A2	Metadata should be accessible even when the data is no longer available.	Metadata has a long-term accessibility plan, exceeding the requirements intended for data.	RFAIR11
I1	(Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.	Metadata use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.	RFAIR12
I2	(Meta)data use vocabularies that follow the FAIR principles.	Metadata uses vocabularies which use FAIR principles.	RFAIR13
I3	(Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data.	Metadata should prefer references to other metadata instead of fixed values.	RFAIR14
R1	(Meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes.	Metadata are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes.	RFAIR15
R1.1	(Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license.	Data licence(s) are chosen and recorded.	RFAIR16
		Metadata licence(s) are chosen and recorded.	RFAIR17
R1.2	(Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance.	(Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance.	RFAIR18
R1.3	(Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards.	(Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards.	RFAIR19

Appendix 3. Analysis of the ENVRI-Hub requirements

The analysis of the requirements for the ENVRI Hub was based on the internal preparation documents, as well as through discussions with the technical development team within the ENVRI FAIR Task Force 6. These (additional) requirements are listed below:

Requirement text	Requirement reference no
Service information (including relevant metadata information) are available for metadata harvesting or upload from RIs.	RHUB1
Digital research assets (including datasets) which are exposed via the ENVRI-Hub have their metadata available in a commonly adopted format.	RHUB2
A machine-to-machine interface exists for access to metadata and (exposed) assets (including datasets).	RHUB3

Appendix 4. Best practices for policy documentation (v.1)

Policies are currently described in many kinds of documents, with widely varying levels of detail, accessibility and availability. As the policies related to EOSC and FAIR are also intended for the user communities, and to show compliance to the EOSC RoP, this can be hard to externally evaluate. Part of this heterogeneity can be linked to the lack of commonly agreed forms for policy documentation. For this reason, ENVRI-FAIR WP4 organised a workshop in the November 2021 to discuss some of the aspects of good policy documentation in the ENVRI research infrastructures. The main aspects of good and interoperable policy documents commonly found within the RIs were as follows:

Availability	Policies should be available in a public repository (e.g., RI webpage), and readable by relevant user communities (usually openly available). Policies and documents they refer to are written, findable and openly available. This means also that all of the RI policies should be clearly visible in their webpages and include the necessary metadata.
Versioned	Policy documents should have versioning systems and consistent dates.
Scoped	Each policy document is clearly defined in the context of other policies. The policy should include information on or links to relevant Practices and Technologies.
Targeted	The policy document should include information on the intended target audiences (including RI positions)
Authorized	The policy document should include information on the authorization (mandate) it has to influence RI operations. In practice this could be a description of the internal acceptance procedure for the RI.
Defined	The terminology and language in the policy document is clearly defined with either an internal glossary or links to relevant vocabularies or documents
Strategic	Policy documents should have relevant links to strategic goals (e.g. policy drivers) it responds to.
Identified	Policy documents should have a globally unique PID, which also enables access to the document
Feasibility	Policy documents should be created with the intent of feasible implementation in the RI, e.g. via linkages to relevant practices, and documentation of resources.
Timeliness	Policy documents should include information on the start of their implementation, and expiry or reconfirmation date. This is important to avoid redundant policies (that may not have been deprecated) which can be considered as policy decisions, but no longer implemented in practice.

Appendix 5 Policies out of scope

- **1. Applicable Legal Jurisdiction**
- **2. Personal (Human rights)**
 - Equality of opportunity / respect
 - Racial (race, colour, nationality); gender; religious/belief
 - Health and Safety
 - Code of Conduct
 - Education & Training
- **3. Business**
 - Mission, Principles
 - Purpose, general principles
 - Stakeholders
 - Customer community, supplier community, external communities (customer and supplier)
 - Objectives
 - Targets to be achieved; timeline; resources
 - Contracts and Agreements
 - Ownership
 - Responsibility (management)
 - Open competition / tendering
 - Contract
 - MoU
 - Financial Management
 - Financial Policy
 - Responsibility and delegated authority
 - Financial reporting
 - Audit
 - Intellectual property (assets)
 - IP Policy (relates to licensing and citation/acknowledgement)
 - Branding

- Risk
- Risk, Severity, Probability, Risk Factor, Mitigation
- **4 Environment**
 - Reduced energy consumption / carbon footprint
- **5 External Activities**
 - Business
 - Responsibility (management)
 - Code of Conduct
 - Cooperative
- **6 Communication**
 - General External Policy
 - Branding, channels, information, feedback
 - Customer community policy
 - Branding, channels, information, feedback
 - RI community policy
 - Branding, channels, information, feedback

Appendix 6 Policies in scope

- Physical Security
- Disaster Recovery
- Privacy
- Authentication
- Authorisation
- Terms and Conditions
- Cookies
- Metadata
- Identifiers
- Licensing
- Curation
- Provenance
- Quality Assurance
- Acknowledgement
- Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)

Appendix 7 EPOS Policy Template

- Why? Do we have a policy and what does it cover
- Who? – target
- Who? – Authors
- When? Is the policy applicable (version, dates)
- Where? Is the policy applicable (countries, regions)
- What?... Is the policy
- How? Is the policy implemented (i.e. relates to which guidelines)